

THE AMERICAN PEDIATRIC SOCIETY'S COLLECTIVE INVESTIGATION ON INFANTILE SCURVY IN NORTH AMERICA

Archives of Pediatrics 1898;XV(7, July):481-508.

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=uva.3470143077&seq=487>

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The 1898 report analyzed data of 379 cases of infantile scurvy seen by 138 physicians. This text extracts primarily the sections of the report that describe the reported symptoms of infantile scurvy.

The cause of scurvy was not known at the end of the 19th century and the sections on etiology and treatment are therefore mostly outdated in the report. However, because scurvy was much more common at that time than currently, and data about the cases were systematically collected for this report, the distribution of symptoms are relevant even currently.

This report was preceded by two reports by Northrup:

Northrup WP. Scorbutus in infants. Archives of Pediatrics. 1892;9(1):1-22.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15463670>

Northrup WP, Crandall FM. Scorbutus in infants. NY Med J 1894;59(May 26):641-6.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15463815>

Yellow is used to indicate the most relevant sections.

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This text is available together with a scanned version of the report at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15282390>

The 1898 report was also published as two parts in the Boston Medical and Surgical Journal (currently NEJM):

Griffith JPC, Jennings CG, Morse JL. The American Pediatric Society's Collective Investigation on Infantile Scurvy in North America. The Boston Medical and Surgical Journal 1898;138(26, June 30):605-9.

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM189806301382601>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15373841>

Griffith JPC, Jennings CG, Morse JL. The American Pediatric Society's Collective Investigation on Infantile Scurvy in North America. The Boston Medical and Surgical Journal 1898;139(1, July 7):3-5.

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM189807071390102>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15373841>

Comments on the report:

Editorial. Infantile scurvy in North America. Br Med J 1898;2(Sept 3):639.

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2434167>

Sutherland GA. Infantile scurvy in North America. Br Med J 1898;2(Sept 10):750.

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2434238>

Marks HM. "Until the sun of science... the true Apollo of medicine has risen": collective investigation in Britain and America, 1880-1910.

Med Hist. 2006;50(2):147-66. [Comments on the 1898 report on pp.160-161]

<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0025727300000132>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1472115>

The Report (1898) has been cited in:

Hess AF. Scurvy, Past and Present. 1920:13,27,28,35,37,49,52,195,200,205,207,226,237,238.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685195> [most important sections]

<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/40505>

<https://digital.library.cornell.edu/catalog/chla2903792>

Hess AF. Infantile scurvy (Barlow's disease). In: Pediatrics, ed. Abt. 1923:849-875.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15465662>

Holt LE. Diseases of Infancy and Childhood. 1919:233-241.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15343352> [chapter on infantile scurvy]

<https://archive.org/details/diseasesofinfanc00holtiala/page/232/mode/2up>

Holt writes:

"For the statistical matter here presented I am indebted to the report of the American Paediatric Society's Collective Investigation of Infantile Scurvy in 1898, embracing 379 cases, reported by 138 observers.

Of these, 31 cases were from my own practice."

Rajakumar K. Infantile scurvy: a historical perspective. Pediatrics. 2001;108(4):E76.

<https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.108.4.e76>

Thomas Barlow

The 1898 report refers repeatedly to “Barlowe” while the correct name of the British paediatrician is Thomas Barlow. In 1883, Thomas Barlow wrote an influential report about children with scurvy, and showed that infantile scurvy was the same disease as adult scurvy. A decade later he discussed further patients with infantile scurvy in his second description of the condition:

Barlow T. On Cases described as Acute Rickets. *Med Chir Trans.* 1883, LXVI, 159.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc2121454> (1883)
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc1975441> (reprint in 1935)

The Bradshaw lecture:

Barlow T. Infantile Scurvy and Its Relation to Rickets. *Lancet.* 1894, II, 1075.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(01\)93995-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(01)93995-9)
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc2405492> BMJ
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/20230441>
<https://archive.org/details/b24905847> The Bradshaw lecture original
<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/um6f7sfm> The Bradshaw lecture original

Chapter on Scurvy in Keating’s *Cyclopædia*, 1889-1892:

<https://archive.org/details/cyclopaediaofdis0002unse/page/264/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/cyclopaediaofdis02keatuoft/page/264/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/cyclopaediaofdis0000john/page/282/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/39002079333093.med.yale.edu/page/264/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/cyclopdiseas02keatgoog/page/264/mode/2up>
https://archive.org/details/cihm_01597/page/n305/mode/2up

Biographies:

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc2056559>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc1987940>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc1550031>
<https://doi.org/10.1017/s002572730005849x>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc1036751>
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-3476\(57\)80317-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-3476(57)80317-5)
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc1561482>
<https://history.rcp.ac.uk/inspiring-physicians/sir-thomas-barlow>
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sir_Thomas_Barlow,_1st_Baronet

The early history of infantile scurvy is summarized in:

Still GF. Infantile scurvy: its history. *Arch Dis Childhood* 1935;10:211-218.
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1975442>
Evans PR. Infantile scurvy: the centenary of Barlow’s disease. *Br Med J.* 1983;287:1862-3.
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1550031>
Hess AF. Scurvy, Past and Present. Lippincott 1920:1-22.
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/40505>
<https://digital.library.cornell.edu/catalog/chla2903792>

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Archives of Pediatrics 1898;XV(7, July):481-508.

The subject of infantile scurvy has so recently come into prominence, and still presents so many mooted questions, especially regarding its etiology, that it was the decision of the American Pediatric Society a year ago to undertake a collective investigation of the matter, based upon the cases occurring in America. This seemed particularly needed, as no other such study upon a large number of cases has yet been made in any country.

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The committee, which is now making its report, was accordingly appointed. It has been diligently at work during nearly a year, and has used every means in its power to reach reports of cases of the disease. A list as accurate as possible was prepared of all the medical journals of North America, and a notice of the proposed investigation was sent to each, inviting correspondence on the part of all readers. Letters were sent to the secretaries of the county societies in a large number of the States of the Union requesting that notice be given at the meetings. Letters were also addressed to the professors of diseases of children in all the regular medical colleges of the United States. The "Index Medicus" was searched for the names of those who had published reports of cases, and letters were addressed to all of them, as indeed to all physicians of whom even the rumor had come of probable cases under their charge. Circulars were printed containing questions to be answered, and were sent to all the members of the American Pediatric Society, to all physicians applying for them, and finally wherever there seemed any chance of getting a response.

The questions contained in the circular requested information on the following points: Whether the case was seen in hospital or private practice; the race, sex, and age; the hygienic surroundings, family history, and previous illnesses; full details of feeding from birth, and the influence which the food appeared to have had upon the development of the disease; the symptoms in detail, with special reference to pain and its location, apparent paralysis or inability to move, swellings, fractures, hemorrhages, the condition of the gums, the presence of fever, the condition of the urine and bowels, the presence of anæmia or mal-nutrition and of rickets or any other complicating diseases, and the character of the first symptom to develop; the treatment in detail, with duration of illness, and the time before decided improvement was discovered; the direct cause of death in fatal cases, and the *post-mortem* findings; and finally, whether the case had been published previously.

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The committee has been surprised and pleased at the large number of replies received. There are other cases of which it has knowledge of which no reports could be obtained, and

undoubtedly many more whose existence was not discovered. But in all the committee has collected 379 cases seen by 138 observers. Some of the cases are very incompletely reported, but in the majority of instances the answers are for the most part satisfactory. No cases needed to be excluded as instances of mistaken diagnosis, although a very few were somewhat doubtful.

[Causes of scurvy are considered in the report, but excluded here]

SYMPTOMS.—The symptoms in infantile scurvy are so typical and well known that they would appear to need little further study. Nevertheless, the attention which has been directed to them by the questions of the circular has not been without fruit.

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FIRST SYMPTOM TO DEVELOP AND ORDER AND TIME OF OTHER SYMPTOMS.—In response to this question the answers have not been altogether satisfactory. Undoubtedly in a large number such early symptoms as anæmia and mal-nutrition were overlooked or were not included by the readers as symptoms of the disease. Then in a large number, perhaps the majority of cases, answers have not made it quite clear whether the correspondent intended that a certain number of symptoms developed in the order in which the names are written, or whether they all were noticed at one time. Presuming that the first is the writer's intention, we make the following statement of the first symptom seen, basing this on 327 cases. The order of symptoms is too complicated and too uncertain to warrant a statistical arrangement.

FIRST SYMPTOMS SEEN.—Pain and tenderness, 145; affection of gums, 42; interference with motion, 36; anæmia, 27; cutaneous hemorrhages, 22; swellings, 16; restlessness, 6; anorexia, 5; debility, 5; diarrhœa, 5; constipation, 2; hemorrhage from nose, 1; hemorrhage from mouth, 1; hemorrhage from rectum, 1; hæmaturia, 3; hæmatoma of tongue, 1; irritability, 3; vomiting, 1; fever, 1; opisthotonos, 1; sweating, 1.

PAIN ON MOTION OR HANDLING.—Pain is clearly a very prominent symptom of the disease. Generally it is evident only when the child is moved, or tries to move itself. Sometimes it is so intense that the approach of any one to the bedside is sufficient to cause the child to scream out through fear of being touched. Pain is reported present in 314 instances. In most of the remaining, no answer was made, and it is probable that the symptom could not have been a prominent one. The locality of the pain in the cases where there were accurate details was as follows:

Legs, 120; legs and arms, 25; legs and one arm, 11; legs and body, 4; one leg, 13; one leg and one arm, 1; one arm, 1; back, 1; back and legs, 1; back and leg, 1; back and thighs, 1; thighs, 1; hips and thigh, 1; one thigh, 2; one hip, 2; knees, 1;

knees and ankles, 2; knees, ankles and shoulders, 1;
knees, ankles and wrists, 2; knees and arms, 1; one knee, 1;
one ankle, 1; ankles, 1; ankles and feet, 1; ankles and elbows, 1;
elbow, 1.

PAIN WHEN AT REST.—In 91 cases pain seems to have been present, even when the child was still; while in 134 it is definitely stated as absent under this condition.

INTERFERENCE WITH MOTION.—The symptom variously described as *paralysis*, *pseudo-paralysis* and *disability* or *unwillingness to move* is reported frequently. It probably depends in every instance upon pain, since there is no evidence that actual paralysis occurs in the disease. In 319 cases interference with motion of this nature existed. p.488

Rigidity is described as present in 96 cases and absent in 106. It is due to pain in most instances, but perhaps in others may have been occasioned or increased by the presence of swelling.

The parts of the body in which motion has been interfered with in any way in the cases reported, and the locality mentioned in detail, may be enumerated as follows:

Legs, 159; legs and arms, 55; legs and one arm, 14;
legs and one hand, 2; one arm, 3; legs and thighs, 1; thighs, 3;
one leg and one arm, 1; one leg, 27; one thigh, 2; hips, 1;
one hip, 2; one hip and thigh, 1; one hip and knee, 3;
hip, leg and shoulder, 1; hip, elbow and shoulder, 1; one knee, 4;
one ankle, 2; ankles, knees, hand and wrist, 1.

POSITION OF THE LIMBS.—To a question regarding the position of the limbs, about which Barlowe¹ speaks so definitely, there have been replies in 205 cases. In 17 of these the position was normal. In the balance we find the position of the limbs as follows:

Flexed, 152; extended, 23; flexed and abducted, 1;
flexed and adducted, 1; flexed and everted, 1; abducted, 1; everted, 3;
everted and extended, 2; toes extended, 1; feet extended, 3.

WEAKNESS OF THE BACK.—The occurrence of weakness of the back, a symptom which Barlowe¹ says is marked, is mentioned as present in 97 of the cases reported to the committee and as absent in 108. In the remaining nothing is said of it.

DEPRESSION OF THE STERNUM.—This condition is likewise emphasized by Barlowe as being sometimes striking and characteristic. It is mentioned in 34 cases, but said to be absent in 170 others. It is not certain in the cases of the report how frequently the condition had developed acutely as a result of scurvy and how often it had already been produced by a previously existing rachitis.

1 See links to Thomas Barlow's papers on page 3 of this document.

SWELLINGS.—The effort has been made by analyzing the cases collected to determine the position of local swellings, whether these were situated in the joints or the shafts of the limbs, in the soft tissues or in the bones, and whether any redness was present. The answers are not clear in every instance, and are frequently somewhat contradictory, partly, perhaps, from failure of the observer to understand the question, and partly from lack of careful discrimination between sub-periosteal and other effusions, and between effusion into a joint and that about it. The great irregularity also of the distribution of the swelling renders an accurate tabular arrangement too complicated. Remembering that in many cases more than one part of the body was involved and that the figures given do not mean that only the portion mentioned is affected in these cases, the following division may be made:

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Joints (or probably oftener about joints) involved in 165 cases.

Location given in 101; viz.:

Knees, 73; ankles, 28; wrists, 12; hand, 1; elbow, 3; shoulder, 5; hip, 6.

Shafts of limbs involved in 179 cases.

Location given in 123; viz.:

Thighs, 59; legs (below knee), 61; “legs” (not further stated), 11; forearm, 5; upper arm, 4; “arm,” 5; ribs, 1; scapula, 1; ilium, 1.

The gross results of the answers regarding the tissues in which the swelling occurred give:

Swelling in soft tissues, 97,
Swelling, sub-periosteal, 114.
Swelling in both situations, 16.

In 69 cases the swollen parts were reddened also. It is stated that there was no redness in 121. **A more general swelling, to be classified rather as œdema, is described in 68 cases** and stated to be absent in 98.

In regard to **the swelling or protrusion of one or both eyes which has been described by writers²,** the symptom is said to have been absent in 110 cases and is reported present in 49. **In 9 of these swelling only is mentioned, in 18 protrusion only, and in 22 both are referred to.**

2 See Zilva SS, Still GF. Orbital hæmorrhage with proptosis in experimental scurvy. Lancet 1920;195:1008.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(01\)08066-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(01)08066-7)

“Out of 64 [human] cases 6 showed orbital hæmorrhage, and in 5 of these there was proptosis ... During experiments on [mangabey] monkeys... a similar occurrence was recently observed... [and also in another] experiment on [rhesus] monkey”

<https://doi.org/10.1002/path.1700220305>

GUMS.—The condition of the gums and mouth is one of extreme interest. In 16 cases it is distinctly stated that the gums were entirely unaffected, while in 313 they were diseased. The degree of involvement varies from slight swelling to great sponginess and even ulceration. The degree and form of the affection in the cases suitable for study may be seen in the following table:

Swelling, absent, 14; present, 293.
Sponginess, absent, 27; present, 249.
Discoloration, absent, 23; present, 259.
Bleeding, absent, 64; present, 188.
Ulceration, absent, 101; present, 91.

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The relation of the affection of the gums to the presence of teeth is of much interest. In nearly all the cases of scurvy in this report teeth were present, but what influence this has is not quite clear, since experience teaches that curiously it is usually the gums of the upper jaw which are most affected, although the lower teeth naturally are the first cut. Statistics on the portion of the gums involved were not furnished sufficiently to allow of conclusions; but regarding the teeth it is to be noted that of 359 cases suitable for comparison, teeth had already appeared in 314 instances, *i.e.*, 87.5 per cent.; while in only 45 cases, *i.e.*, 12.5 per cent., were there no teeth. In studying more carefully these 45 cases of scurvy without teeth, we may make the following analysis:

No teeth; gums normal, 21 cases.

No teeth; gums affected, 24 cases.

The conditions present in the latter group were as follows:
Swelling, 19 cases; sponginess, 14 cases; bleeding, 5 cases;
discoloration, 17 cases; ulceration, 4 cases.

This is a proof that affection of the gums may occur equally well when there are no teeth as when teeth have developed. The fact that in the great majority of cases of infantile scurvy the presence of teeth and the affection of the gums is associated, depends merely on the fact that the disease generally develops at an age when teeth naturally have been cut.

CUTANEOUS HEMORRHAGES.—These have occurred with frequency in the cases reported. Accurate data are given in 353 cases. Of these, cutaneous hemorrhage is reported present in 182 and absent in 171. There is much doubt about the accuracy of the writers in their classification of the hemorrhages according to size, and the proper use by them of the descriptive names employed, inasmuch as the question on this point did not specify clearly. In 99 instances the presence of “ecchymoses” is mentioned. In 83 “purpuric eruption” is reported and in 37 “petechiæ.” In 13 the nature of the lesion is not specified.

HEMORRHAGE FROM MUCOUS MEMBRANES.—Data are available in 361 cases. Of these there were no hemorrhages from any mucous membrane in 196, while in 164 they occurred. In 93 cases there was hemorrhage from the mouth. This includes the cases where bleeding from the gums is described by writers. In 33 cases there was bleeding from the nose; in 2 from the stomach, and in 37 from the bowels. Cases of hæmaturia are not included here, and will be referred to later.

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FRACTURES.—Fractures in infantile scurvy are usually separations of the epiphyses merely. Even this would seem to be rare, for fracture of any kind is mentioned in only 9 of our cases. In 342 it is distinctly stated to have been absent, and in the remaining the question is not answered.

FEVER.—Probably in the majority of the cases of the disease upon which this report is based no temperature record has been made. In 93 cases it is stated that there was no fever; in 182 it was present and in the remaining no answer is given. In the cases where present it is described as slight in 116 instances, moderate in 23, high in 8, and irregular in 6. Clearly, fever is not a prominent symptom of the disease, and probably often, when present, depends on accidental causes.

BOWEL MOVEMENTS.—The following conditions are mentioned:

- Bowels regular, 74.
- Bowels irregular, 15.
- Constipation, 126.
- Diarrhœa, 65.
- Bloody diarrhœa, 12.

URINE.—Judging from the number of instances in which no answers have been returned, no examination of the urine has been made in most of the cases. It is reported as examined for albumin in 163 cases; in 33 of these albuminuria is reported and in 130 it was absent. Tube casts were present in 13 instances, absent in 13, and no observation reported in the others.

Properly speaking the occurrence of hæmaturia should be discussed under the title of hemorrhage. It is mentioned as present in 22 cases only.³ Of other abnormal conditions of the urine the following may be mentioned: Urine very acid, 1; urine scanty, 9; urine suppressed, 1; urine increased in quantity, 3; glycosuria, 1; hæmoglobinuria, 1; pus (from cystitis), 1; phosphates increased, 1; chlorides increased, 1.

ANÆMIA; MAL-NUTRITION.—These conditions, already referred to as often the earliest symptoms of infantile scurvy, may have been the first evidences of the disease in many of the cases on which this report is based. In other cases they must be regarded as complicating affections only. Answers are not full enough to allow of satisfactory conclusions on this point.

Anæmia is said to have been present in 254 cases, as follows:

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Anæmia present (without specifying degree), 47.

Anæmia slight, 66.

Anæmia moderate, 32.

Anæmia marked, 109.

Blood examinations were made in 15 cases and the conditions noted as follows: The percentage of hæmoglobin was much reduced in all the cases, 8 in number, in which an examination was made, some being as low as 35 per cent. Of the 7 cases in which the red blood corpuscles were counted, all showed a reduction except 2. In these 2 the number was normal or nearly so, but the hæmoglobin was 50 and 35 per cent., respectively. Leucocytosis was present in 5 cases. Poikilocytosis⁴ in 2. In only one instance was there a differential count of the leucocytes made.

3 George Still considered that hæmaturia was common.

Still G. Common Disorders and Diseases of Childhood. 1915.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15342856>

“sixty-four cases under my own observation” p.110; “I have examined the urine of all cases under my notice as far as possible... the proportion showing hæmaturia was 60 per cent. But it must not be supposed that blood is to be detected by the naked-eye appearance of the urine in this proportion of cases. In many the amount of blood was so small that it was seen only by careful microscopic examination.” p.115

Still GF. Nephritis in infantile scurvy. Lancet 1904;164:441-442.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(01\)08116-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(01)08116-8)

“so far as my own observations go, it would seem to be the rule rather than the exception to find that the urine in any case of pronounced infantile scurvy contains either a trace of albumin or blood... The two cases recorded here seem to be of interest as showing, so far as can be shown from clinical evidence alone, that infantile scurvy may produce not merely albuminuria or hæmaturia but actual nephritis.”

4 Poikilocytosis: red blood cells with abnormal shapes

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Poikilocytosis>

Of 217 cases in which the question is answered, *emaciation* is recorded in 167 and is said to have been absent in 50.

Mal-nutrition was observed in 178 cases out of 216; in which replies were made as follows:

Mal-nutrition present (without specifying degree), 108; slight, 20; moderate, 7; marked, 43.

[Considerations of the relation between scurvy and rickets are excluded here]

DIAGNOSIS.—The study of diagnosis has been only incidental, based upon the mistakes made before the disease was recognized in certain cases. The only disease for which infantile scurvy was repeatedly taken appears to have been rheumatism. In several instances the affection of the legs was supposed to be due to sarcoma. The apparent paralytic condition has also been the cause of error in some instances.

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DURATION OF ILLNESS AND PROGNOSIS.—The disease is essentially chronic; its course terminating only on the institution of proper treatment. This seems to be proved by the answers contained in the circulars. To the question concerning the *duration of the disease before the case came under observation*, replies were received in 306 cases.

Table⁵

Intensely interesting in this connection are the replies to the next two questions: First, *Duration of illness after treatment was commenced*, and second, *Duration of treatment before marked improvement was noticed*. To the first question replies concerning 308 cases were received. Of course those fatal during the attack of scurvy are not included here nor those which passed from observation.

Still more striking are the answers to the second question, as to the time when marked improvement was first noticed. There are 311 cases suitable for study in this category, excluding fatal cases and those passing from observation as before. The replies are often astonishing. Nothing is more striking than the speed with which these reports show a grave constitutional disease disappearing under proper treatment. There is certainly no disease for which a more specific treatment can be said to exist. The replies to the last two questions may be conveniently stated in the following tables:

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5 See the scanned Table at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15282390> p.493

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=uva.3470143077&seq=499>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15373841> p.4

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM189807071390102> p.4

DURATION OF TREATMENT BEFORE MARKED IMPROVEMENT WAS NOTICED

Days	Cases	Weeks	Cases	Months	Cases
1	19	1	47	1	6
2	58	2	27	2	4
3	46	3	8	3	4
4	26	4	1		
5	19	5	1		
6	1	6	1		
7	2				
8	2				
9	1				
10	7				
12	2				

Reported as prompt recovery, 13; at once, 15; immediately, 1.

[Marked improvement in 2 days in 20% (77/379), and in 1 week in 58% (218/379)]

DURATION OF TREATMENT BEFORE RECOVERY WAS COMPLETE

Days	Cases	Weeks	Cases	Months	Cases
1	6	1	48	1	28
2	5	2	54	2	14
3	14	3	36	3	5
4	8	4	14	4	2
5	5	5	6	5	1
6	1	6	14	6	2
8	2	7	1	7	1
10	17			8	1
12	3			9	1
13	3				
15	2				
16	1				

Reported as immediate, 4; almost immediate, 9.

[Complete recovery took over 1 month in 13% (48/379)]

[Reported treatments excluded here]

FATAL CASES.—Twenty-nine of the 379 cases are reported to have died. In 2 of these, death seems to have been remote from the attack of scurvy. Of the remaining 27 the causes as enumerated by the reporters are as follows:

p.498-499

Exhaustion, 6; cerebral hemorrhage, 3; diarrhœa, bronchitis, 2; vomiting (?) 1; convulsions, 1; pneumonia, 4; malnutrition, 1; pulmonary hemorrhage, 1; ulcer of stomach, 1; syncope and nephritis, 1; doubtful, 4.

It is difficult to determine in how many of these the scurvy itself could be held responsible for the death; probably in few if any.

AUTOPSIES.—There have been handed in to the committee the reports of 6 autopsies in all, some of them only partial. The salient points of each may be enumerated as follows:

Case of Dr. A. Caille. Child of nine months, ill about three months. Autopsy showed **hemorrhagic spots on the pericardium and surface of the liver**; sub-periosteal hemorrhage of the long bones.

Case of Dr. L. E. Holt.⁶ Child of twelve months: ill for two months. Autopsy showed separation of the lower epiphysis from the shaft of the left femur; extensive sub-periosteal hemorrhage of the left femur; **sub-pleural hemorrhages; broncho-pneumonia.**

6 L Emmett Holt wrote a book chapter about infant scurvy:

Holt LE. Scorbutus (Scurvy). In: The Diseases of Infancy and Childhood. 6th ed., 1911:233–241. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15343352>

Holt writes about autopsies, p.235:

“I have myself had the opportunity of making examinations in three cases. The findings are remarkably uniform, but represent, of course, the extreme results of the disease. **The most striking lesion is subperiosteal hæmorrhage**, which is practically constant and may occur almost anywhere in the body, but affects chiefly the bones of the lower extremities; it is often very extensive, and may reach from the knee to the great trochanter, or from the ankle nearly to the knee. **Extravasations may also be found between the muscles, and blood may infiltrate the cellular tissue in the neighbourhood of the joints.** Besides these lesions resulting from hæmorrhagic periostitis the bone itself may be affected. Separation of the epiphysis from the shaft of some of the long bones, generally at the lower end of the femur or lower end of the tibia, is found in most of the fatal cases. Notwithstanding the serious lesions near the large joints, the joints themselves are usually normal.

The minute bone changes are somewhat similar to those of rickets. But there are also differences of importance. **The disposition to hæmorrhage, which is altogether the most characteristic feature of scurvy**, is entirely wanting in rickets. The visceral lesions are inconstant. Those most frequently found are small **hæmorrhages beneath the pleura, pericardium, and peritonæum, sometimes into the various organs, also broncho-pneumonia, and nephritis.** There may be small extravasations found upon the surface of any of the mucous membranes. The alterations in the blood-vessels are undoubtedly an important factor in bringing about the disposition to hæmorrhage, but as yet they have been very imperfectly studied.”

Case of Dr. L. E. Holt.^{6,7} Child of thirteen months: ill about two months. Autopsy showed sub-periosteal hemorrhage and separation of the lower epiphysis of the left femur; hemorrhages into the muscles of the left thigh, swellings about the opposite knee and both ankles; knee-joints normal; minute sub-pleural hemorrhages; well marked exudative nephritis; minute hemorrhages on the surface of the liver.

Case of W. P. Northrup.⁸ (The first autopsy in the United States). Child of eighteen months; ill about one month. Autopsy showed sub-periosteal hemorrhage of both tibia and both femora; detachment of the lower epiphysis of the left femur and maceration of lower end of shaft; broncho-pneumonia of left lung; no rachitic or syphilitic changes on microscopical examination.

7 This case is "Case IX" in:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15463670>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=uva.3470143072&seq=25>
and "case 11" in:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15463815>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=nnc2.ark:/13960/t5v724829&seq=656>

8 In the 1894 report (Case 2), Northrup wrote about this autopsy, p.2-3:

"The important features in the pathological anatomy of scurvy are well illustrated in the asylum case already referred to. The gums showed the characteristic signs of hæmorrhagic gingivitis, being dark, spongy, and bloody. The main interest otherwise lay in the condition of the legs. The left thigh was symmetrically enlarged, but both thighs were above normal in size. The femur was normal at its upper extremity. The lower half was invested with a black, grumous, subperiosteal layer of blood. The lower epiphysis was detached and the lower end of the shaft macerated, eroded, and soft, lying loose in the black, disintegrating blood clot. The tibiæ were surrounded by thin, dark, hæmorrhagic layers beneath the periosteum, and the proximal portions of both were congested. The fibulæ and the bones of the upper extremities were normal. The accompanying illustration was drawn from a specimen which consisted of a lateral half of the lower limb of the less affected side. Microscopical examination of the bone disclosed no syphilitic or rhachitic changes, and no inflammatory changes in bone or periosteum. The softened, macerated bone gave no evidence of suppuration, but there was moderate congestion of the femur and the upper extremity of the tibia."

New York Medical Journal, May 26, 1894.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15463815>
<https://resource.nlm.nih.gov/101747078>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=nnc2.ark:/13960/t5v724829&seq=655>

This is also "Case II" in:

Northrup WP. Scorbutus in infants; American cases. Archives of Pediatrics. 1892;IX:1-22.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15463670>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=uva.3470143072&seq=13>

Case of Dr. L. Starr. Child of thirteen months; ill for three months. Autopsy showed “right leg from knee to ankle stuffed with a puffy mass replacing normal tissue. Separation of both bones one inch above ankle.”

Case of Dr. C. W. Townsend. Child of ten months; ill three to four weeks. Autopsy showed **bloody serum in pleural cavity**; perforating ulcer of the stomach; tubercular (?) process in peritoneum.

In conclusion the committee would thank publicly their correspondents who have sent their reports of cases and who are enumerated below. They are also greatly indebted to Dr. Wm. Schleif of Philadelphia for valuable aid in analyzing the circulars received and tabulating the results.

Committee, Signed,
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[The report includes a 9-page Discussion which is not included here]